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METHODS FOR EVALUATING ENVIRONMENTAL AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY FOR ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. The article examines issues regarding the assessment of the ecological and economic efficiency of environmental protection activities. An accessible methodology for assessing the environmental and economic efficiency of small enterprises that do not produce material goods has been proposed.

Keywords: green office, environmental efficiency, economic efficiency, small enterprise, resource conservation.

Introduction

The global environmental movement is continuously developing. The number of companies striving to have as little impact on the environment as possible is constantly increasing. Various countries are developing an organization management concept that will reduce the negative impact on nature. To eliminate, level, and reduce the negative impact of the industrial complex on the natural environment, it is necessary to develop strategies for managing environmental impact at regional and local levels. To achieve this, environmental management systems, as well as elements of the enterprise's environmental policy and all related documentation, are implemented. At the same time, control tools are developed, such as establishing control environmental and economic performance indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of the enterprise's adopted strategy. At the same time, a comprehensive approach must be used, i.e., a list of measures to reduce the negative impact of production must be developed, i.e., environmentally safe and energy-efficient equipment, as well as the best available technologies, must be implemented. Few enterprises utilize such approaches, as it is often more profitable for the enterprise to pay a fine than to change technological processes, as this involves costs and requires investments of a different nature.

Literature analysis on the topic

Various methods for assessing the environmental and economic efficiency of enterprise activities are described. N.B. Sukhomlinova and E.G. Aksyonova classify the following as the main criteria for the ecological and economic efficiency of environmental protection measures:

- inclusion of environmental costs and benefits in cash flows, which are taken into account when analyzing activities and modeling cash flows;
- accounting for the time factor as one of the tools for reflecting the long-term environmental and social consequences of environmental protection measures;
- accounting for the possibility of underestimating environmental benefits and natural benefits in the analysis due to lack of data, difficulties in obtaining them, and describing these benefits and benefits in qualitative indicators;
- flexible selection of methods and calculation methodologies, based on the availability of methodologies suitable for assessing the consequences of a specific type of impact and their feasibility, the availability of source information, the time for analysis, and available financial resources;
- comparing socially desirable results and private interests to analyze the possibility of eliminating emerging contradictions in the early stages of decision-making and to analyze the distribution of benefits and costs between different parties;
- using "cost-effectiveness" analysis when conducting traditional "cost-benefit" analysis is impractical or impossible, for example, in cases where benefits cannot be presented in monetary terms [1; 5].

To evaluate the environmental and economic efficiency of environmental protection activities, the authors recommend using the following indicators:

- net present value;
- internal rate of return;
- cost-benefit ratio [1; 6; 7].

In the works of various authors, a number of formulas are provided for calculating and evaluating the ecological-economic efficiency of environmental

protection activities, taking into account the indicators mentioned above [The same source].

Research methodology

The comparative and economic-statistical analysis methods served as the methodological basis for this article. Along with this, the research process employed methods of observation, data collection and processing, analysis and generalization, grouping, comparative analysis, monographic study, as well as systems approach and comprehensive analysis.

Analysis and results

As we know, the company's environmental strategy is currently formed based on business interests, image, and the state of the region's environment. In recent years, the production activities of enterprises have become environmentally responsible, and they are ready to bear full responsibility for their negative impact on nature. Almost all enterprises solve their environmental problems based on their own funds, without utilizing foreign investment reserves or state programs.

For over 25 years, the "Ecology" national project has been implemented in Uzbekistan, aimed at solving financial issues regarding environmental problems, and industrial enterprises within the framework of this national project have been able to receive funding for environmental protection measures and the modernization of technological complexes. At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2025 was declared the "Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy," within the framework of which it is possible to obtain grants and subsidies for the implementation of the best available technologies and the implementation of corrective measures that allow for the greening of production activities. Therefore, to date, achieving economic efficiency in production in conjunction with ecological and economic efficiency remains relevant.

Economic efficiency (production efficiency) is the ratio between the economic result and the costs of production process factors. To quantitatively determine economic efficiency, the efficiency indicator is used; it is also the effectiveness of an

economic system, expressed in the ratio of the useful final results of its functioning to the resources expended [2].

Environmental efficiency (ecological characteristics) – the measurable results of the environmental management system related to the organization's control of its environmental aspects based on its environmental policy, as well as targeted and planned environmental indicators [The same source].

The advantages of the presented approaches and methods for assessing environmental and economic efficiency are: versatility, reliability, and objectivity of assessment. The methodology is being successfully implemented using the example of enterprises in the production sector.

However, for small enterprises whose primary activity is non-material production, the methodology is not always applicable. The main reason is that in small enterprises, as a rule, the internal resources for an analyst position are insufficient to conduct such a large-scale and detailed analysis, or often there is simply no analyst position.

In this regard, the need for simpler methods for assessing the environmental and economic efficiency of small non-production enterprises, where personnel work is organized in office spaces, is becoming increasingly relevant.

Such enterprises and companies are characterized by the constant consumption of resources and material goods - water, electricity, paper, etc. To evaluate the environmental and economic efficiency of a small enterprise (office) in the non-production sector, we propose using the following criteria:

- environmental efficiency;
- economic efficiency;
- impact on corporate culture.

Measures to increase the environmental efficiency of the company's activities are proposed in works reflecting the "Green Office" program[3; 4] (*The "Green Office" (eco-office) program is a set of measures to reduce negative environmental impacts and ensure the rational use of resources. It combines technical solutions (energy*

conservation) and employee environmental education, while simultaneously reducing business financial costs. Implementing the concept not only helps protect the environment but also creates a positive image for the company).

To calculate environmental efficiency, quantitative indicators can be applied, both measurable (the amount of saved resources) and calculated. For example, conversion to CO₂ equivalent is used as the calculation method [Thus cited].

Another example is the number of "living" trees: one ton of waste paper saves 10–17 trees (terek, pine, fir, and birch) [8].

In the activities of a small enterprise, priority is given to costless or low-cost activities for office greening, namely:

- saving electricity;
- heat saving;
- saving water resources;
- saving paper and consumables;
- information support.

1. Electricity saving involves the exclusion of incandescent lamps, except in cases where their use is mandatory for technological considerations or safety considerations; in the case of luminescent lamps, the most effective lamps of this class are used if possible. Furthermore, where applicable, it is advisable to use an automatic lighting control system (photorelay, motion sensors).

2. Heat savings can be optimally ensured through the use of manual or automatic control systems heat supply, excluding the use of windows to regulate indoor temperature. Such a system must provide for temperature regulation depending on the presence of employees in the premises.

3. To save water resources, it is necessary to install devices that ensure water consumption reduction (for example, special nozzles for jets), water consumption meters, and payment for water consumption based on their readings.

4. Saving paper and consumables involves printing draft documents on the back of office paper. It is also advisable to exclude the use of single-use dishes.

If such a refusal is impossible for hygienic reasons, preference is given to single-use items made of moisture-resistant cardboard, which are subsequently transferred for recycling.

The economic efficiency of the aforementioned measures can be easily evaluated using the following calculation method:

$$EE = RE - Z$$

Where,

EE - economic efficiency of measures;

RE – cost of saved resources;

Z – costs for conducting activities (purchasing equipment, etc.).

Conclusions and proposals. Information support plays a special role in the process of implementing the "Green Office" concept, which is widely used by enterprises in Uzbekistan. Information, including visual agitation, promoting energy- and resource-saving technologies, is posted in office premises. The economic costs of conducting environmental advocacy may be almost zero, but the economic effect is significant.

Information support, along with a complex of other measures, contributes to changing the employees' attitude toward nature and their awareness of their own role and significance in solving environmental problems.

Analysis of the results of implementing environmental measures under the "Ecology" project showed that most of these measures do not require significant economic investment. The economic efficiency of such measures is achieved by increasing the level of environmental culture among employees and, consequently, reducing the consumption of resources and material goods.

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